

THE RUSSIAN-ARMENIAN LOGISTICS FORUM IS THE SCIENTIFIC BASIS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSPORT COMMUNICATIONS BETWEEN RUSSIA AND ARMENIA

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Abstract. *On November 17-25, 2022, the Rostov branch of the Moscow State Technical University of Civil Aviation, with the active participation of the RANEPa, held an international logistics forum dedicated to the day of transport workers.*

The forum opened with the international conference “Air transport - the basis of logistics communications”. Conferences under the general name “AviaTrans” have been held at the Rostov branch of MSTU GA since 2011 and this conference was no exception, it was unusual for the conference to be included in a single logistics forum, which started on November 17, 2022 at the Rostov branch of MSTU GA and ended on November 25, 2022 at the Government House Republic of Armenia. The designated forum was held at the initiative of the Ministry of Economy within the framework of the Program of International Cooperation between the Government of the Russian Federation and the Government of the Republic of Armenia, signed on December 22, 2021.

Keywords: *forum, international conference, cooperation, program, international.*

Representatives of the sectors of the Russian and Armenian economy, the scientific and expert community, developers of new technological solutions came together to exchange experience and hold fruitful discussions within the framework of the international forum. The event has become a platform for establishing useful contacts between scientific organizations and enterprises of the Russian Federation and the Republic of Armenia.

The opening of the forum in Rostov-on-Don gave a powerful impetus to the implementation of the entire event. Hundreds of scientists and practitioners discussed the problems and prospects for the development of logistics communications between the Russian Federation and the Republic of Armenia. The participants were welcomed by the First Deputy Chairman of the Committee on CIS Affairs, Eurasian Integration and Relations with Compatriots of the State Duma of the Federal Assembly of the Russian Federation Viktor Vodolatsky, who noted: “the high level and qualifications of the conference participants, representatives of the sectors of the Russian and Armenian economy, the scientific and expert community, developers of new technological solutions – will create the basis for a meaningful discourse”.

As part of the sectional hearings, the conference participants discussed a wide range of issues: from innovative technologies in air transport to aviation education. It is noteworthy that

this year, in addition to the traditional sections of the conference, a meeting of the new section “Logistics communications in air transport” was held, the creation of which was a logical response to the challenges of our time. In his welcoming speech at the plenary session, Valery Silaev, head of the Southern Interregional Territorial Administration for Air Transport “Rosaviatsia”, emphasized the importance of the university for civil aviation and recalled that he himself was a graduate of the Rostov branch of the Moscow State Technical University of Civil Aviation.

Deputy Head of the Department of State Aviation Supervision and Supervision of Transport Security in the Southern Federal District of the Federal Service for Supervision in the Sphere of Transport Alexander Pavlovich Podgorny emphasized:

– This representative international forum is one of the most important events for the development of aviation. The conference is a discussion platform, and I am convinced that holding this event will become an incentive for further fruitful work.

Deputy Governor of the Rostov Region, Minister of Transport of the Rostov Region Vladimir Okunev noted the organizers of the forum with diplomas and thanks; The Executive Director of Azimuth Airlines in his greeting emphasized the importance of the university for the airline. Director of the Rostov branch of the Moscow State Technical University of Civil Aviation Victoria Pashinskaya noted that the Rostov branch of the Moscow State Technical University of Civil Aviation is a higher educational institution that has been providing personnel to all aviation enterprises in the South of Russia for more than half a century. This year, the university entered into an agreement with the Governor of the Rostov region and the Azimut airline, aimed at training personnel for the civil aviation of the region.

Chairman of the Organizing Committee of the International Russian-Armenian Logistics Forum, Head of the Department of Socio-Economic Disciplines of the Rostov branch of MSTU GA Professor Grigory Akopov emphasized that the decision to hold a logistics forum was made in connection with the licensing of a new area of training - Technology of transport processes, profile “Organization of transportation and management in air transport”, and the initiative to hold the Russian-Armenian event came from the Ministry of Economic Development of the Rostov region.

The AviaTrans-2022 conference, which opened the Russian-Armenian Logistics Forum, is the largest industry event in the field of scientific and practical research of civil aviation and has been held since 2010 on the basis of the Rostov branch of MSTU GA. In 2022, not only the traditional partners of the university, but also a number of organizations that had not previously visited the Rostov branch of the Moscow State Technical University of Civil Aviation actively joined the event. In Rostov-on-Don, the permanent partners of the university from the RANEPa, SFU, DSTU, branches of the Russian State Humanitarian University, MTUCI and the Customs Academy, as well as representatives of a number of universities that took part in the event for the first time, actively participated: Pyatigorsk State University, Radiotechnical Institute named after A.L.Mints, Southern Scientific Center of the Russian Academy of Sciences, Military Academy of the General Staff of the Armed Forces of the Russian Federation, Krasnodar Higher Military School, Azov-Chernomorsk Engineering Institute - a branch of the Don State Agrarian University, Institute of Water Transport named after G.Ya. Sedov, Air Force Academy named after professor N.E.Zhukovsky and Yu.A. Gagarin and a number of other universities. Thus, a delegation from the Peoples’ Friendship University of Russia headed by Professor Valery Takazov flew to Yerevan to finish the forum. The Russian-Armenian University was represented by Professor Vahe Davtyan

and lecturer Nina Margaryan, whose presentations aroused great interest and lively discussion. The Academy of Public Administration of the Republic of Armenia was represented at the event by Rector Khachatour Kazeyan and Head of the Center for International Cooperation and Development Teresa Khechoyan. Associate Professor of the Armenian State University of Economics, economist Aghasi Tavadyan, within the framework of the round table, demonstrated the results of his research on forecasting the growth of cargo transportation between Russia and Armenia. In a remote on-line format, the round table was actively attended by colleagues from the SRIM RANEP, who not only asked questions, but also participated in the discussion.

The end of the Forum was held in Yerevan on November 25, in the building of the Government of the Republic of Armenia within the framework of the round table: “New facets of the development of Russian-Armenian logistic and migration processes” organized by the Rostov branch of MSTU GA with the assistance of the Chinese Center for Science and Culture of the Republic of Armenia.

Director of the Chinese Center for Science and Culture of the Republic of Armenia Isabella Muradyan, who has been specializing in migration issues for many years, made a presentation: “New Trends in the Development of Russian-Armenian Logistics and Migration Processes”. Many figures and data aroused keen interest.

As Isabella Muradyan noted: “Today, only air transportation and the land route through Upper Lars really work for both cargo and people”.

“Hypothetically, it is supposed to unblock all transport communications in the region. Particular emphasis is placed on the unblocking of regional railway communications. The route “Kars (Turkey) - Gyumri (Armenia) - Nakhichevan (Azerbaijan) - Meghri (Armenia) - Baku (Azerbaijan) - Iran or Russia fork”. Sections “Kars-Dogukapi” (Turkey) and “Akhuryan-Gyumri” (Armenia), the roads are blocked by Turkey and Azerbaijan and have not been operated for more than 30 years, moreover, the Turkish-Armenian section is not electrified, as well as the internal section on the territory of Turkey itself going to Armenia from Erzurum / Western Armenia, today - Turkey. Another road that is important for the development of Armenian-Russian logistics relations is the Batumi (Georgia) - Akhaltsikhe /Samtskhe-Javakheti, an Armenian-populated region of Georgia / -Yerevan (Armenia) - 448 km highway - also practically does not operate. It is extremely important because it is part of the international North-South highway between Iran and Armenia,” she stressed.

I. Muradyan was in Akhaltsikhe in 2015, earthworks were going on near Abastumani. And already in 2022, travelers from the Russian Federation write - Along the “road of death” through Khulo and Akhaltsikhe: “Although somewhere in the Khulo region we saw a Turkish asphalt plant down on the river bank. That is, the Turks seem to be repairing the road. But I just checked Google Maps, and there all the photos that are for 2016 and 2017 show the same example”. The author contacted her Georgian colleagues and we were told that now the Batumi-Akhaltsikhe road, including 7 bridges, is being built at an accelerated pace by Chinese companies and they will complete it by 2024.

No less interesting was the speech of Alexei Sandykov, MP, Chairman of the IPA CIS Standing Committee on Economics and Finance, delivered at the Russian-Armenian Forum. She appeared in the first lines of the news feeds of the Republic of Armenia for several more days.

Particular attention was paid to the problems of logistics processes by the Head of the Union of Commodity Producers of Armenia, Chairman of the Commission of the Public Council of the Republic of Armenia Vazgen Safaryan, who actively participated in the forum.

It is noteworthy that in his report at the round table, Professor Grigory Akopov spoke not only about the training of personnel for the effective functioning of the civil aviation of the Republic of Armenia, but also explained the prospects for a new direction of training in the profile "Organization of transportation and management in air transport". Training for professional activities of specialists in the field of transport logistics will contribute to the development of logistics processes between our countries in the future, he noted.

Of great interest was the report of Professor V.S.Davtyan, which considered the challenges of the transport development of Armenia in the context of geopolitical transformations in the South Caucasus. The main risks and prospects for unblocking transport communications in the region are established in the context of Armenia's long-term interests. Problems that impede the full-fledged transport integration of the South Caucasus and contribute to the formation of new threats to the transport security of the countries of the region are identified. Scenarios for unblocking transport communications in the region are considered in the context of the formation of international transport and logistics corridors "North-South" and "East-West".

As Professor Davtyan noted: "The search for ways of full and organic integration into international transport corridors is the most urgent challenge for Armenia, since it is the diversification of transport communications that is able to increase the level of the country's transport security, and therefore, can positively affect the functioning of the national security system in general. For a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of this problem, it is necessary to identify the specifics of the main international transport and logistics projects of integration interest for the Republic of Armenia, as well as to identify the main geopolitical and geo-economic factors hindering its integration into international transport corridors".

As a result of the events held, a collection of abstracts⁴ was published and the conclusions of the forum participants were reflected in the media, and also sent to various authorities. Thus, the conclusions made by the experts are communicated to the general public and sent to decision makers.

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